

The Digital Toolkit for Collaborative Environmental Research

DIGITCORE

The DIGITCORE Toolkit was designed as an interactive digital site.
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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
I. Introduction	4
Origins	4
Competing Perspectives on Open	4
A Shifting Landscape	5
Framing Our Findings as a Toolkit	5
Values	6
The Research Process	6
II. Themes and Patterns	8
Theme: Ensuring benefit to frontline communities	8
1. Pattern: Enhance frontline communities' agency	8
2. Pattern: Respect frontline communities' time and effort	10
3. Pattern: Reduce harm to communities	11
4. Pattern: Hold outsiders accountable	12
Theme: Practicing Openness	14
5. Pattern: Open means different things to different people	14
6. Pattern: Mandated vs. meaningful openness	15
7. Pattern: Pressure to commercialize	16
8. Pattern: Openness as a daily practice	17
9. Pattern: The limits of open tool usability for frontline communities	18
Theme: Data ≠ information	20
10. Pattern: Adequate metadata requires capacity	20
11. Pattern: Lack of standardization for data quality	21
12. Pattern: Isolated open data repositories	22
13. Pattern: Meaning-making takes resources	23
Theme: Academic culture and norms	25
14. Pattern: Frontline communities' and academia's differing norms, time frames, and practices	25
15. Pattern: Readiness for collaboration	27
Theme: Situational collaboration practices	28
16. Pattern: Overly complex governance	28
17. Pattern: Partners and clients have different needs	29
18. Pattern: Iterative tool development can create instability	30
19. Pattern: Plan for the future	30
Theme: Long-term sustainability	33
20. Pattern: Open tools need ongoing maintenance	33
21. Pattern: Balancing Scale and Specificity	34
22. Pattern: Champions within civil society organisations need more support	35
III. Acknowledgments	36
IV. Glossary	38

I. Introduction

Openness is often regarded as an inherent good, valued for its promises of transparency, accessibility, and collaboration; we wanted to understand how these ideals are realized in practice for communities facing the direct consequences of environmental and climate harm.

The Digital Toolkit for Collaborative Environmental Research (DIGITCORE) synthesizes what we learned when we asked: *How is “open” experienced by frontline communities participating in environmental research?* We present the findings of our research as a toolkit—in the form of values, themes, patterns, solutions, and resources—with the goal of offering technologists and researchers collaborating on open infrastructure an interactive tool to support their practice. We each know our own craft, but often lack the tools for genuine collaboration; this toolkit focuses on where changes in process or design can make a meaningful difference.

Origins

This project emerged from the question: does the Free and Open Source narrative of inclusivity, transparency, and accessibility correspond with the actual inclusion of frontline communities in open technology projects for environmental monitoring and sustainability? Quickly, though, we realized that the answer wasn't straightforward. To understand why, we needed to start a bit further back to examine how frontline communities actually experience the practice of “open”.

Drawing on our backgrounds in environmental research and involvement in open source technology, communities, and projects, we approached this work with the recognition that “open” can mean very different things depending on one's position, power, and proximity to decision-making. Our goal was to trace the tensions between ideals and lived experience and to create a practical resource for researchers and open developers navigating these dynamics.

Competing Perspectives on Open

In the last five years, open science has seen a surge in popularity. “Open technologies” (such as Free and Open Source Software, open data, and open hardware) [have become prominent in public debate](#) concerning the present and future of our digital infrastructures. Governments, international agencies, and funding organizations are beginning to understand the positive effects that “openness” could have in science and technology and are shifting their policy and funding priorities accordingly, making it easier for people to collaborate on a larger scale and utilize public resources more effectively.

While there are clear definitions of open source infrastructure, based on rules governing open technology and tools, we took a broader view of “open infrastructure” in the context of DIGITCORE: in practice, the

concept of openness does not stop at a definition or rules applied to technology. It also applies to the context in which these technologies live – the practices and relationships established through and by their use, in our case, to produce and share data and knowledge about environmental issues relevant to frontline communities.

Even with this broader perspective, openness is not universally embraced. “Openness” is often perceived warily by communities that have been historically excluded from science and technology projects. This difference in perception can fuel tensions and misunderstandings between environmental scientists and technologists who are hopeful about open science, and “frontline communities” that bear the brunt of climate change and environmental pollution.

A Shifting Landscape

In the United States, [\\$1.6 billion in federal spending](#) was allocated during the Biden administration to address environmental pollution and climate change, especially at the community level. Environmental research saw increased funding levels, accompanied by clearer mandates for the development and release of [open technologies and research practices](#). In practice, however, the disconnect between pollution and climate-affected communities and technoscientific initiatives remained, as support for digital infrastructure and connectivity was underemphasized.

In 2025, we’ve seen an abrupt and direct retreat from scientific and environmental progress in the U.S. While this trend is still evolving, it aligns with global developments: according to a [report from OECD and the United Nations Development Program](#), climate action is losing momentum, and at the start of 2025, there was a low proportion of countries complying with the Paris Agreement’s commitment to submit national policies established to address climate change.

In this shifting landscape, environmental researchers and developers of open technologies have found themselves caught in the middle. New attention to and support for environmental and climate justice from national governments and global institutions have proven vulnerable to rapid rollback by governments, leaving the future of environmental research projects, especially those undertaken in collaboration with frontline communities, in jeopardy. Open science was initially viewed by policymakers as a desirable approach to advancing environmental and climate knowledge; now, with the withdrawal of public support for scientific research, openness presents strategic opportunities for researchers and communities to preserve and continue their investigations and their work toward justice. Yet, frontline communities continue to have good reasons to worry that the pursuit of open science could perpetuate extractive relationships, increase their vulnerability to violence, and/or undermine their economic security.

This project has become increasingly necessary as shifting political will, uncertain funding landscapes, and escalating climate crises make it critical to examine whether open technology efforts are truly inclusive of the communities most affected by these issues. These realities shaped how we approached DIGITCORE, not just as a study, but as a practical toolkit to support people in responding to these dynamics.

Framing Our Findings as a Toolkit

Openness is not a static description of a tool or a piece of software; openness is an ongoing practice. This toolkit is intended to be a resource for researchers (including both civil society organizations and academics) and open developers and technologists attempting to navigate these complex dynamics. While frontline communities also have a role to play in constructively navigating the tensions that openness can bring, we focused primarily on what researchers and developers can do to avoid placing

additional burdens on communities that are already navigating the daily demands of climate and environmental challenges.

By centering governance, accountability, and collective care, alongside the practices and technologies of open infrastructure, the DIGITCORE toolkit provides actionable steps and resources that enable researchers and developers to build relationships and practices that meaningfully include and support the urgency of frontline communities' work.

Values

The DIGITCORE toolkit aims to ground open infrastructure development in the practice-based work of organizers and their collaborators. To situate the themes, patterns, solutions, and resources, we've articulated the values that openness aspires to—values identified by research participants who are using, or considering using, open infrastructure to support collaborative environmental research. These values are at the core of each pattern in this toolkit, and in some instances are shared as solutions in and of themselves.

Openness is tailored.

Digital tools are used in unique contexts where culture, geography, ecosystems, politics, and economics collide. Open infrastructure should provide situational flexibility regarding how information is collected, analyzed, maintained, protected, used, and made available (or not) for sharing.

Open infrastructure prioritizes mobilization.

Open technologies are implemented by individuals and organizations whose role is to motivate, engage, and encourage communities. Open practices, tools, and objects should enable action.

Flexibility is a feature.

Organizing work needs to adapt to potentially rapid and urgent shifts in policy, politics, or environmental conditions. Relatedly, communities understand how external attention to the issues they face comes in cycles. The development of open infrastructure should be responsive to the varying timelines and circumstances faced by different communities.

Open infrastructure upholds place-based care.

Environmental justice efforts generate strategies to take care of places and the people who live there. Open infrastructure must be developed in conversation with, and in relation to, community practices of care.

Open infrastructure meets the demand for readily available information.

Open infrastructure and tools should facilitate the accessibility and availability of information in a timely manner, enabling communities to make informed decisions.

Open infrastructure addresses prohibitive costs.

Open infrastructure makes it possible to produce, share, maintain, and use information in an accessible way.

The Research Process

In our research, we asked how is openness experienced by frontline community members? We were interested in understanding if there were points at which frontline communities felt that information faced

enclosure, if openness was limiting in other problematic ways, or if openness offered noticeable benefits or opportunities.

We established criteria to be more specific about the interests driving our questions. Projects needed to (1) examine issues of concern to frontline communities, (2) include the participation of community members (in some form), and (3) create, use, or attempt to use open infrastructures. These criteria were shaped as a result of early discussions about how openness could be explored as a spectrum in the context of environmental research with frontline communities. This framing allowed us to consider infrastructures as both the tools and relationships among actors, helping us to hypothesize about the trade-offs that may lead to different approaches to this research.

The research consisted of four main components: (1) mapping relevant initiatives, (2) conducting focus groups, (3) conducting interviews, and (4) holding feedback and review sessions. As we developed the resulting toolkit, we also collaborated with participants and colleagues to design and operationalize the research findings.

We employed this combination of research techniques to investigate the development, dissemination, and application of open tools and approaches for environmental data collection, analysis, and visualization. We approached the initial mapping work by identifying databases related to participatory science initiatives and projects from around the world, and querying them for lists associated with environmental themes. We then selected and contacted those that were being developed with a degree of participation of frontline communities (at any phase of the research process), and created, used, or attempted to use a tool or set of technologies identified as open or an open-proprietary hybrid.

Building on a project list and our inclusion criteria, we then hosted a series of focus groups that examined the perceived “limits of openness” as experienced by community organizers and nonprofits, socio-environmental researchers, and open technology developers. During the focus groups, we asked research participants to elaborate on the challenges they perceive in the context of their projects, as well as their general perceptions of open technologies (such as open data and open research software) and the role that they play in the present and future of environmental research.

In our semi-structured interviews, we originally planned to explore in more detail the difficulties and solutions experienced with respect to community-based stewardship of common resources, with an interview protocol derived from results obtained during the focus groups. In these, we identified that the perspective from developers of open tools and technologies was not fully explored and may imply different challenges to the advancement of open infrastructures in environmental research. A series of interviews with developers connected to tools used in projects and initiatives related to environmental issues of community interest allowed us to explore the dimensions of openness associated with how these communities of practice engage or fail to engage with others when designing and implementing technological decisions. We asked the developers about their iterative processes and the mechanisms they use to communicate and consider the interests and needs of frontline communities or their organizations.

In total, we hosted sixteen workshops, focus groups, interviews, and office hours. This allowed us to provide ample opportunities for participants to review progress and provide feedback throughout the project's duration.

II. Themes and Patterns

This toolkit is first and foremost intended for open technology projects, developers, and researchers (all of whom may include members of frontline communities). These are our primary audiences because they are often the individuals encountering the “boundaries of open” and seeking effective strategies to produce and manage environmental data in the public interest. Our emphasis on these groups tries to turn on its head the reality that frontline communities are often the ones expected to adapt their practices to fit the frameworks of research initiatives or government procedures. That said, community organizations, as well as research institutions and funders that support, resource, and govern these other groups, will find valuable solutions and resources throughout this toolkit.

Through our research, several themes emerged that have helped organize the patterns we surfaced. While these themes are often interrelated, they group together distinct needs, practices, and realities that different audiences experience and navigate.

We use patterns as the basic unit of this toolkit to describe challenges, problems, and phenomena experienced or observed by our participants. Pattern language is also commonly used by software engineers.

Theme: Ensuring benefit to frontline communities

Within the development of open infrastructure, ensuring benefit to frontline communities means going beyond access and inclusion to prioritizing ownership and collaboration. This involves sharing leadership in decision making, providing resources for collaborating, minimizing harm and maximizing benefit, supporting indigenous data sovereignty, and creating accountability mechanisms.

1. Pattern: Enhance frontline communities’ agency

- a. **Description:** Communities’ agency is respected when they are able to lead or co-lead in decision-making. When researchers or technology developers set goals without community input, they risk overlooking local knowledge and undermining self-determination. For example, analyzing monitoring or sensor data without input from or discussion with communities risks sharing incomplete knowledge that can demotivate

further collaboration or intervention as analytical assumptions might not reflect the communities' lived experience. Achieving this level of input from communities may demand forms of communication that go beyond typical research or technology development activities, such as participating in community organizing activities, sharing stories, or simply one-on-one or in-person conversations.

b. **Audiences:** Researchers, OS developers

c. **Solutions:**

- i. **Collaborate on goals over time:** Co-develop research and/or design goals, prioritizing transparency in decision making and flexibility throughout the research or design process. Researchers and developers support community agency and indigenous data sovereignty when they remain flexible and transparent, recognizing that community members may hold heterogeneous views or that priorities may evolve over time.
 - See Resources i, vi, vii
- ii. **Secure consent before sharing:** Discuss the possibility and methods of sharing information and publicizing research outputs, as well as the mechanisms through which they will be shared. Obtain community consent before sharing. For indigenous data in particular, consider the use of data licenses or labels for respecting cultural protocols around the sharing and use of knowledge.
 - See Resources ii, iii, iv
- iii. **Let communities own their data:** Ensure that communities can retain control over data about them or collected by them. Work towards reaching agreements that clearly delineate what can be shared publicly. Explain to users that they have influence over the data production and sharing process and what your role is within it. When using open platforms and repositories to share data or documentation, opt for those that enable differentiated access and privacy.
 - See Resources iv, v
- iv. **Start with the community:** Prioritize interventions and practices that support or leverage communities' known and accepted settings and activities. This might include creating documentation in local languages, and requesting input or sharing results at existing community meetings. Create opportunities for community members to lead or co-lead when it comes to making decisions.
 - See Resources vi, vii

Resources

- i) [Animikii's Pathfinding process](#) supports co-design of technology, specifically with Indigenous communities.
- ii) [LiteFarm's Informed Consent Form and Privacy Policy](#) is a good example of a mechanism for obtaining informed consent to share environmental data collected by individual community members—in this case, farmers using the open source LiteFarm app to record information about their farm management practices, which includes potentially sensitive data.
- iii) [OpenTEAM's Data Use Documents](#) include good examples of tools to request and manage consent to share or use data. In particular, see the Agriculturalists' Bill of Data Rights and the Data Hosting and Storage Agreement.
- iv) [Local Contexts' Data Labels](#) identify and clarify indigenous communities' rules, expectations, and responsibilities for Traditional Knowledge and Biocultural information.
- v) [OEDP's Tools and Templates for Community Data](#) support community data stewards in being able to safely and equitably use and share community environmental data. You can find things

- like a co-ownership agreement template and data sharing agreement questions. The [Data Co-ownership Template](#) and “[Our Data, Our Rules](#)” zines are particularly relevant.
- vi) [The Data Ethics Toolkit](#) from the Association for Advancing Participatory Sciences includes a worksheet on “Recompense,” or ensuring appropriate benefits and recognition to communities.
 - vii) The [University of Reading’s Participatory Action Research Toolkit](#), developed from the real-world experiences of community members and researchers, guides community researchers through the process of building trust, sharing power, and fostering the relationships needed to make a genuine impact.

2. Pattern: Respect frontline communities’ time and effort

- a. **Description:** Research activities can be time-consuming, especially if community members are involved in analysis and interpretation. Community members may question whether the time and energy spent participating in research will result in meaningful outcomes for them. This may be the case *even if* community organizations initiate research projects or acknowledge the need for more technical or scientific approaches to building evidence that can inform policy or advocacy. Participants may lose motivation, especially when academic or technical objectives overshadow community priorities.
- b. **Audiences:** Researchers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Align research expectations:** Co-develop short-term and longer-term research agendas. Aligning on these and transparently setting expectations from the outset can help to maintain trust and participation. Participatory diagnoses and community-defined indicators of success can also help clarify what is achievable and valuable for everyone involved.
 - See Resources i
 - ii. **Tailor outputs to the context:** Prioritize generating practical and situated outputs, rather than only theory-oriented or academically-focused outputs like journal articles, scientific papers, or reports. More situationally helpful outputs could include data products, like datasets or tools, to support continued data collection and analysis.
 - See Resources i, ii, iii
 - iii. **Map stakeholder power and interest:** By mapping power relations, you might identify people who can ally with your work, or further its intended impact (e.g., interested policymakers).
 - See Resources iii
 - iv. **Value community spaces and time:** Show up in community spaces when invited (or when open to the public) and offer to support work that may not directly align with your priorities, but has been identified as central to the project and collaboration by your partners. Allocate financial or other development resources to compensate community participation in collaborations.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org

Resources

- i) The [CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance](#) provide a framework for considering the collective benefit of data collection and use activities, specifically for Indigenous data and collaboration.
- ii) AGU's [Thriving Earth Exchange](#) has shared resources for co-producing research and advancing outcomes rather than just standalone products.
- iii) [Research for the Frontlines](#) provides a model for cooperative environmental research wherein volunteer academics respond to community requests for research support.
- iv) [The Collective Power Playbook's Starter Advocacy Strategy Play](#) provides a group exercise how-to for stakeholder mapping. While not all collaborative research efforts will focus explicitly on advocacy strategy, this exercise can help collaborations think through who has power and influence in a given arena, and how to engage them.

3. Pattern: Reduce harm to communities

- a. **Description:** Communities may hesitate to engage in research or collaborative efforts, fearing immediate risks to their safety, dignity, or livelihoods. They may also have deep-rooted mistrust stemming from prior experiences with extractive practices, such as data collection without reciprocal benefit or even intimidation of community members. In contexts involving open infrastructure, concerns around [biopiracy](#), misuse of shared data, or potential exploitation can further compound reluctance. For example, sharing raw environmental sensor data (e.g., about wildlife locations, or air quality indicators) can be misused by commercial interests or bad actors. Community members might fear being stigmatized or criminalized as a result of sharing information that could identify them on any technology—open or proprietary—that lacks clearly defined privacy protections.
- b. **Audiences:** Researchers, OS developers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Invest in data privacy and security:** Assess the risks of data sharing and affirm communities' rights *not* to publish information. Supporting community-led risk assessments, or facilitating these in collaboration with community members, can also enhance community agency. Identify and apply strong security, anonymization, and privacy practices, and share and discuss these practices with community members. If necessary, avoid collecting sensitive data at all. But if you must, have plans to anonymize data on two axes: obscuring identifying information of people (e.g., for storing survey data) and of sensitive locations (e.g., observations of endangered or at-risk species).
 - See Resources i, ii, iii, iv
 - ii. **Develop data use and sharing agreements:** Co-develop and use data sharing agreements to delineate how data can be used—and under what conditions. These agreements can help you anticipate potential harms by identifying safeguards in advance, establishing reporting procedures, and setting expectations for accountability in case of harm.
 - See Resources v
 - iii. **Plan for sustained investment:** Invest the, often large, time commitment needed to have closer, face-to-face, and sustained interactions with communities, especially if access to or sharing of community data will continue beyond a time-bound project. Ensure that community members are compensated

for their time. Similarly, cooperative ownership models can also distribute the financial responsibility for maintaining services among the organizations that rely on them.

- See Resources vi

Resources

- i. [The Data Ethics Toolkit](#) from the Association for Advancing Participatory Sciences includes worksheets on data governance and report-outs that can help you think through and plan for possible risks associated with community data.
- ii. The [NIST Privacy Framework](#), developed by the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology, helps organizations manage risks by building privacy into their data processing systems.
- iii. [SAFETAG](#) is a professional framework designed to help civil society organizations assess and improve their digital security. Tailored for low resource contexts, it combines digital security auditing with organizational change. In the site, you can find instructions for creating a [risk matrix](#) and [conducting a data assessment](#).
- iv. A Better Deal for Data's [Eight Commitments](#) are a good model for pledges to protect communities and their data.
- v. [OEDP's Tools and Templates for Community Data](#) support community data stewards in being able to safely and equitably use and share community environmental data. They include tools like a data values statement template and data use and sharing agreement questions.
- vi. In '[Designing a data cooperative to help make our homes more energy efficient](#),' Open Data Manchester shares their experience with bringing various small cooperatives together into one larger one.

4. Pattern: Hold outsiders accountable

- a. **Description:** Research practices, even when well-intentioned, can cause harm, especially if transparency and shared decision-making are not prioritized. Time and capacity constraints in academic and tech spaces can lead to a common practice of asking for forgiveness rather than permission; this can backfire easily in community collaborations. When methods or goals shift without consent, communities may feel misled or harmed, even if apologies follow.
- b. **Audiences:** Researchers, OS developers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Develop community agreements and review boards:** Establish shared agreements and community review processes before initiating research or development projects. These agreements should outline project roles, data ownership, and decision-making structures, as well as expectations and accountability measures. Community review boards can also be created and consulted at key stages to provide feedback and ensure that agreements are being followed.
 - See Resources i
 - ii. **Establish feedback loops:** Integrate feedback mechanisms into research projects and digital tools. This could be as simple as prominently featuring a

feedback form on an online platform or as involved as check-ins, webinars, a user forum, or user feedback sessions beyond a time-bound project.

- See Resources iii, iv
- iii. **Develop mediation techniques from the start:** Moments of conflict can become opportunities to build trust if harm is addressed openly and with humility; and if clear efforts are undertaken to make repair or change future practices. To support this, team members should take basic facilitation and mediation training, particularly in well-funded projects.
- See Resources ii

Resources

- i. [OEDP's Tools and Templates for Community Data](#) support community data stewards in being able to safely and equitably use and share community environmental data. They include tools like a data values statement template and data use and sharing agreement questions.
- ii. [FabRiders](#) offers facilitation workshops and an active community of practice focused on facilitative techniques.
- iii. This [article by MoldStud](#) explains the critical role of user feedback in open source software, detailing how it helps identify bugs, prioritize features, and improve the user experience. It outlines practical strategies for collecting feedback such as surveys, forums, feedback forms, and user testing; it also emphasizes best practices like prioritizing feedback, iterative development, and transparent communication with users.
- iv. This [resource from Listen4Good](#) describes the core competencies organizations need to establish and sustain high-quality feedback loops with their stakeholders, especially in the social sector. It provides a framework and practical guidance for nonprofits to systematically collect, analyze, and act on feedback, ensuring that client and community voices directly inform program improvements and organizational decision-making.

Theme: Practicing Openness

Openness is a core principle of open infrastructure, but its meaning and implementation can vary widely. To find alignment on what open means to different stakeholders necessitates: balancing mandates alongside community privacy, addressing commercialization pressures, and creating processes to make openness a daily practice. You can read more on our findings around openness in the introduction.

5. Pattern: Open means different things to different people

- a. **Description:** Different interpretations of "open"—whether referring to open data, open source software, or open engagement practices—can influence a project's direction or lead to disagreements in design. For some, open tools must be intuitive and usable; for others, open means transparent, modifiable, or redistributable. Differing interpretations can cause misalignments in both design and collaboration. For example, a research project might publish data openly on an institutional repository, allowing access to community members, but it may not include contextual information or be provided in a usable format, preventing its local understanding and application. Data may be shared publicly, but remain in PDF format or embedded in poorly structured websites: these can be particularly difficult to work with, giving the appearance of transparency without enabling meaningful access, reuse, or understanding of the information.
- b. **Audiences:** Researchers, OS developers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Write a charter on openness:** Explicitly define what openness means in the context of your specific research agenda or technology project. Involve different stakeholders and participants in this process. This may include creating a shared definition, or a shared understanding of how these different stakeholders are defining it in their different contexts.
 - See Resources i, ii
 - ii. **Articulate user personas:** Develop user personas that exemplify different interests and needs around openness.
 - See Resources i, ii
 - iii. **Provide context for shared data:** True openness requires more than accessible formats: it also needs context and structure to give the data meaning and make it usable. Explainers, descriptive information, metadata (ideally in standardized formats), visualizations, and clear or verified schema or ontologies can provide helpful context to support use beyond your original intent. Additionally, including

the license under which the data can be used ensures that others understand how the data can be reused, adapted, or redistributed in different contexts.

- See Resources iii, iv, v, vi
- iv. **Adopt open standards:** Adopt and discuss open standards for data formats, metadata, and software interoperability with your community partners. Open standards reduce barriers to entry and allow for broader discussions on what parts of a project are open and how.
- See Resources vii, viii

Resources

- i. The values statements at the beginning of this toolkit offer some possible ways that different stakeholders value openness, or want to see research or technology practices apply and demonstrate openness. Likewise, working principles for collaborations can be a useful way for people to understand where asynchronous decisions-making can happen and when decisions should be brought back to the group.
- ii. OEDP's [Community Data Playbook](#) compiles case studies and strategies related to environmental data governance. The case studies are examples of community-based or collaborative environmental data efforts that demonstrate different needs, interests, and capacities in regards to openness. The accompanying [Resource Library](#) includes resources such as a template for creating values-oriented project ReadMes.
- iii. [NFDI's Ontology Collection](#) is a searchable library of catalysis ontologies that can be applied or expanded depending on your research's context. It includes several ontologies related to environmental data.
- iv. [ENVO](#) is a community-driven ontology designed to help both humans and machines consistently describe environmental entities. It is a FAIR-compliant resource that promotes interoperability by providing controlled, concise descriptions of environmental concepts, and offers tools for annotation, browsing, and community contributions.
- v. The [Semantic Sensor Network Ontology](#), developed by W3C and OGC, provides a standardized framework for describing sensors, their observations, related procedures, and the features or properties they monitor.
- vi. [SPARQL](#) is the query language and protocol used for retrieving and manipulating data stored in Resource Description Framework (RDF) format.
- vii. [LinkML](#) is a general purpose modeling language that can be used with linked data, JSON, and other formats. Their cookie cutter template allows users to describe the structure of their data in a standardized way.
- viii. Participatory frameworks and tools, such as [Participedia](#) and [Living Labs toolkits](#), offer methods for engaging with communities to achieve alignment.

6. Pattern: Mandated vs. meaningful openness

- a. **Description:** Researchers must often respond to funder or institutional requirements or requests to make their data public. Without conversations around frontline community privacy or security needs, and without adequate training, researchers may inadvertently share data in ways that harm frontline communities' interests. These interests may include common concerns with sensitive or personally identifiable information, but may also relate to community members' agency and ownership over information about them or collected by them. For example, community members may simply want to know how

their data is being used outside of initial research projects. Or they may want to impose restrictions on different users or types of use, or even reject the possibility of data being publicized due to potentially negative economic effects on their subsistence activities or ownership rights.

b. **Audiences:** Researchers

c. **Solutions:**

- i. **Blur data:** Aggregate or otherwise de-identify published or shared versions of datasets to make it difficult to identify individuals.
 - See Resources i
- ii. **Agree on data licensing and sharing agreements:** Co-develop, discuss, and use data licensing and sharing agreements to delineate how data can be used and under what conditions. These can help identify safeguards, establish reporting procedures, and provide a mechanism for accountability in case of harm.
 - See Resources ii, iii

Resources

- i. [J-PAL's Guide to De-identifying Data](#) includes various processes for de-identifying data to reduce the risk of harm to individuals.
- ii. [OEDP's Tools and Templates for Community Data](#) support community data stewards in being able to safely and equitably use and share community environmental data. They include tools like data use and sharing agreement questions.
- iii. [Local Contexts' Data Labels](#) identify and clarify indigenous communities' rules, expectations, and responsibilities for Traditional Knowledge and Biocultural information.

7. Pattern: Pressure to commercialize

- a. **Description:** As open source tools in environmental research gain traction through wider adoption, external stakeholders such as funders or universities often ask about their business models. They want to understand not only the return on their initial investment, but also the long-term path to sustainability to reduce reliance on grant funding. This often results in a tension between maintaining openness and achieving perceived “commercial value” that can result in locking down (parts of) a tool to manage risk or enable monetization. However, open source does not necessarily limit financial value as it can reduce duplication and is at times more financially viable.
- b. **Audiences:** OS developers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Explore revenue sharing models and dual licensing:** As revenue generation is often necessary to sustain tools in the long-term, consider models that don't require you to limit access to tools or data, as well as approaches to distributing revenue in ways that can support the communities with whom you have collaborated, even if indirectly.
 - See Resources i, iii, iv
 - ii. **Establish stewardship agreements:** Establish clear stewardship agreements that define how the project will be maintained and governed, and evolve over time. These agreements should clarify decision making power among contributors and community members, safeguard community interests, and

define how profits will be disbursed if or when the pressure to commercialize arises.

- See Resources ii
- iii. **Engage with a fiscal sponsor:** Fiscal sponsorship is a model in which a nonprofit organization offers its legal and tax-exempt status to groups or projects engaged in activities aligned with its mission. This can be especially useful if the project would like to apply for and receive grants or donations for continued development.
 - See Resources iii, iv, v

Resources

- i. [Open Source Project Revenue Strategies: Sustainable Funding for Free Software](#) covers revenue sharing models such as donations, support services, and dual licensing models for free and open source projects to adopt.
- ii. The Gathering for Open Science Hardware (GOSH) has shared [Community Distributed Manufacturing Templates & Procedures](#) to support the stewardship of open or shared infrastructure, in this case open scientific instruments. This template has been used by the [OpenFlexure project](#) who receives a portion of revenue from at least one of their vendors.
- iii. Special organizations exist for the purpose of fiscally sponsoring projects. While each project has individual needs that should be independently assessed, a non-conclusive list of Fiscal Sponsorship providers includes: [Open Source Collective](#), [Aspiration Technology](#), [Allied Media Foundation](#), [Code for Science and Society](#), and [Open Science Hardware Foundation](#).
- iv. "[Open hardware is economically efficient and generates a massive return on public investment](#)" shares helpful framing for how free and open source hardware enables scientists to build custom scientific tools at a fraction of the cost of proprietary alternatives.
- v. If you need to advocate for the cost savings of using open source tools, "[The Value of Open Source Software](#)," analyzes the economic and social impact of open source software (OSS) by quantifying both its supply-side and demand-side value. And "[Economic savings for scientific free and open source technology: A review](#)" is a study conducted on the potential economic savings of using open source hardware.

8. Pattern: Openness as a daily practice

- a. **Description:** Openness is often framed as a goal or value, but it can be most effectively pursued when it becomes ingrained in workflows, relationships, and assumptions. In many cases, openness emerges not from formal declarations or requirements, but from the way people effectively work together day-to-day. Practices that help us build an environmental research commons—like sharing resources, communicating transparently, or making decisions collaboratively—can be woven into workflows, relationships, and assumptions, even when there's no explicit "open" label.
- b. **Audiences:** Researchers, OS developers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Integrate community practices:** Map practices already used by the communities with whom you are collaborating, and incorporate these where possible into your own research or design workflows. This will, in turn, make it easier for your research or tool to be useful for the communities themselves.

- See Resources i, ii
- ii. **Incorporate open habits:** Embed openness practices, such as version control and thorough documentation, into individual, project, and team workflows.
 - See Resources iii, iv, v, vi, vii
- iii. **Develop relational openness:** Build in time for cultivating the relational aspects of openness, such as participation and transparent decision making, in addition to incorporating the technical aspects of openness, like digital infrastructure, licensing, and open documentation.
 - See Resources i

Resources

- i. [CommunityRule](#) is a toolkit for structuring collaborative governance and role-sharing useful for the concept of "open maintainers."
- ii. [Fostering Participatory Data Stewardship](#) by the Aapti Institute provides sector-specific guidance around participatory mechanisms for data governance.
- iii. The [OpenFlexure Project](#) provides a model for open, user-focused documentation in the open hardware space.
- iv. The Engine Room offers practical guides on documentation catered to working with civil society organizations including [documenting when there's so much other work to do](#) and [creating documentation for non-technical audiences](#).
- v. Organizations like [Openscapes](#) offer training on embedding open practices into collaborative and scientific workflows.
- vi. [The Turing Way](#) and [OpenSciency](#) are both free training resources for learning about and integrating open practices into workflows.
- vii. [Protocols.io](#) is a platform for sharing community-reviewed, reproducible protocols. It enables researchers to publish, discover, and collaboratively improve experimental methods, ensuring transparency and repeatability in scientific workflows.

9. Pattern: The limits of open tool usability for frontline communities

- a. **Description:** While standardized transparency and documentation practices can showcase an open source tool's validity and sustainability, frontline communities may not have the technical capacity to use or replicate them. Some tools often assume stable internet access, powerful computers, and high levels of digital literacy, some or all of which may not be present in a frontline community. Free tools also often require a lot of time and resources to develop or maintain, leading many communities to opt for low-cost proprietary tools. Community projects often find it most effective to use a hybrid open-proprietary approach. For others, the distinction between open source and proprietary tools may not even be a major consideration for various reasons (e.g., as lack of awareness of the differences, easy use being a priority).
- b. **Audience:** Researchers, OS developers
- a. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Map the technology ecosystem:** Work with research collaborators or users to map their communities' technology needs and the infrastructure that would support these. Be thoughtful about when and how open and digital technologies are used and use them only when they add value. Remember that openness can mean different things to different people.

- Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
- ii. **Find power users:** Identify and support power users to assess the accessibility needs of different actors and improve tools' accessibility and usability within communities. You can do this by organizing hackathons or workshops to test tools and identify interested or technically inclined community members. Provide resources and compensate these users.
 - See Resources i
- iii. **Design for multiple user types:** Aim to design tools that require minimal training and maintenance, or use a variety of design features tailored to varying levels of experience and data requirements. Additionally, ensure documentation is created with diverse user types in mind, providing clear guidance for both novice and advanced users.
 - See Resources ii, iii
- iv. **Build layered accessibility:** Offer different levels of accessibility, such as intuitive interfaces for community members, and customizable options for more experienced users.
 - See Resources ii, iii
- v. **Develop community talent:** Offer training through workshops and mentorship programs. Invest in training community members as maintainers or trainers for other community members.
 - See Resources i

Resources

- i. The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement provides resources and training on investing in and supporting “community champions” or power users. See their [Community Champions program resources](#).
- ii. [Inclusive Components](#) is a hybrid blog and design pattern library aimed at designing inclusive web interfaces at the component level. While aimed primarily at accessibility, the patterns are useful for addressing varying user needs.
- iii. FrontlineSMS discusses how they used [limitation as a design philosophy](#) when developing tools that bridge the gap between highly technical users and frontline communities.

Theme: Data ≠ information

Open infrastructure should go beyond making data available; it should also aim to make it understandable, usable, and trustworthy. This can be accomplished through adequate metadata, consistent quality standards, and interoperable systems, as well as resources and support for communities to interpret data.

10. Pattern: Adequate metadata requires capacity

- a. **Description:** Metadata, or information about data, is essential for enabling reuse, ensuring transparency, and supporting long-term impact. Communities often lack time or training to generate or document metadata, especially after data has already been collected or uploaded. However, ensuring metadata is thorough and useful requires planning, resources, and capacity.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers, Researchers
- a. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Plan for metadata early:** Integrate metadata creation into the initial phases of project planning. Define what metadata will be collected, by whom, and using what tools. In this process, assess what metadata would be essential to helping an outsider understand the data's context. Assign responsibility for documentation as you would for data collection.
 - See Resources i
 - ii. **Reuse and adapt standards:** Start with existing metadata standards or vocabularies relevant to environmental research. Adapt them as needed to fit the skills and context of your community.
 - See Resources i, ii
 - iii. **Co-develop with contributors:** Engage data contributors in shaping what metadata fields are collected and how. Co-design fosters ownership of the process and ensures that metadata accurately reflects local knowledge and values.
 - See Resources i
 - iv. **Build metadata into workflows:** Use structured workflows (such as survey tools, mobile apps, or shared online forms) that capture metadata at the point of data entry. Automating or simplifying this process increases compliance, consistency, and accuracy.
 - See Resources i
 - v. **Use guided tools:** Point-and-click upload tools, especially those with built-in metadata templates, checklists, or validation steps, can lower barriers for contributors unfamiliar with metadata standards.

- See Resources ii
- vi. **Offer lightweight training:** Provide accessible training materials (e.g., short videos, one-pagers, or walkthroughs) on what metadata is and why it matters. Use real-world examples to show how good metadata improves usability.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org

Resources

- i. [Metadata Game Changers](#) provides consultation and a process for evaluating, documenting, and recording research metadata.
- ii. The [Dublin Core Generator](#) is a tool for generating Dublin Core code that is easy to use, flexible with regards to tagging, and updated to the most recent Dublin Core standards.

11. Pattern: Lack of standardization for data quality

- a. **Description:** Open data platforms may integrate information from multiple sources, they may provide access to raw data, or both. There are few standardized ways to integrate information from multiple sources, which can make it difficult to both ensure data accuracy and build user trust. Many open hardware tools also use proprietary, platform-specific, or non-standard data formats, which limits transparency and collaboration. In the long term, these challenges require high-level policy guidance and coordination to harmonize QA/QC practices across platforms or networks, as well as an acknowledgement that data quality practices may depend on the goals of the research (e.g., interpretation for policy making, advocacy, or science). In the meantime, data portal maintainers are left to navigate a difficult balance between transparency, data quality, and usability in the absence of such standards.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers, Researchers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Ask for user feedback:** Enable users to interact transparently with data by flagging anomalies, commenting on data points, and submitting proposed corrections or metadata clarifications.
 - See Resources i, vii, viii
 - ii. **Follow standard operating procedures (SOPs):** Define and implement clear SOPs for data collection, processing, and quality control. Provide public documentation and versioning so users can trace decisions in order to better understand the reasoning behind the processes.
 - See Resources ii, iii, iv, v
 - iii. **Define tiers of data quality:** Provide different quality levels (e.g., raw, processed, validated) to accommodate various user needs while maintaining transparency.
 - See Resources iii, vi
 - iv. **Track data provenance:** Track and display metadata on data origin, processing steps, timestamps, and responsible parties to support interpretability and trust.
 - See Resources iii

Resources

- i. [GitHub](#) provides mechanisms for flagging issues on open software and files as well as creating a space for discussion.
- ii. [Protocols.io](#) is a platform for sharing community-reviewed, reproducible protocols. It enables researchers to publish, discover, and collaboratively improve experimental methods, ensuring transparency and repeatability in scientific workflows.
- iii. [Data Management Skillbuilding Hub](#) provides comprehensive guidance on data management, curation, and quality control. The hub offers practical resources, tutorials, and best practices to help researchers enhance the integrity and usability of their data throughout the research lifecycle.
- iv. [Open Geospatial Consortium](#) set global benchmarks for geospatial data sharing and integration. These standards facilitate seamless data exchange and ensure high-quality, interoperable geospatial information across different platforms and applications.
- v. [Research Data Alliance](#) is a global community dedicated to advancing data standardization and sharing best practices. Their recommendations and outputs help researchers to overcome barriers to data sharing, foster collaboration among researchers, and promote open science worldwide.
- vi. The Wilson Center's [Open Science Hardware: A Shared Solution to Environmental Monitoring Challenges](#) outlines the potential of open science hardware to benefit environmental monitoring efforts in tribal, local, state, and federal governments. It also explores strategies to address current barriers and accelerators to impact.
- vii. Open Knowledge has developed the [Open Data Editor](#) which helps users [detect errors](#), check for correct data formats, and even publish their own data on open data portals.
- viii. [OpenAQ](#), which curates air quality measurements, also provides access to their underlying [metadata](#) editor.

12. Pattern: Isolated open data repositories

- a. **Description:** Environmental and scientific data is often siloed in isolated repositories, project-specific databases, or organizational websites. These systems typically lack interoperability and cross-repository search capabilities, making it difficult for researchers, policymakers, and local communities to locate, access, and synthesize relevant data. This fragmentation hampers collaborative research and informed decision-making but also poses a risk to the long-term preservation and stewardship of critical environmental datasets.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers, Researchers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Map and assess available infrastructure:** Audit the tools and platforms you use for storing and sharing environmental data, identifying both robust platforms and gaps in the landscape.
 - See Resources i, ii
 - ii. **Develop or adopt federated data platforms:** Look for platforms that allow distributed repositories to interoperate while maintaining local control over data.
 - See Resources ii, iii, vii
 - iii. **Promote the use of common metadata schemas and open standards:** Adopting common metadata schemas and open standards into your own work

can improve discoverability and usability across systems while contributing to standardized qualities.

- See Resources ii, iii, iv, v, vi
- iv. **Incentivize repository linkage and data sharing:** Work to build links between data sets through shared platforms, open and interoperable data standards, and accessible methods for requesting data.
- See Resources ii, iii

Resources

- i. The [General Repository Comparison Chart and FAIRsharing Collection](#) describes the specifications and differences of several widely used and well-resourced open repositories, aiming to help researchers make decisions about selecting a general repository.
- ii. [Re3data.org](#) is a comprehensive global registry that catalogs research data repositories across all academic disciplines, making it easier for researchers to find suitable platforms for data sharing and preservation.
- iii. [Current CoreTrustSeal](#) offers a widely recognized certification for data repositories, signifying adherence to international standards for reliable and sustainable data management. This certification helps researchers and institutions identify repositories that are committed to long-term data stewardship, security, and accessibility.
- iv. [Research Data Alliance](#) is a global community dedicated to advancing data standardization and sharing best practices. Their recommendations and outputs help researchers to overcome barriers to data sharing, foster collaboration among researchers, and promote open science worldwide.
- v. The [Environmental Information Exchange Network](#) has a list of approved exchange network data standards.
- vi. The [Ecological Metadata Language](#) (EML) defines a comprehensive vocabulary and a readable XML markup syntax for documenting research data. It is in widespread use in the earth and environmental sciences, and increasingly in other research disciplines as well. EML is a community-maintained specification, and evolves to meet the data documentation needs of researchers who want to openly document, preserve, and share data and outputs.
- vii. [Internet of Water's Principles](#) is a set of guidelines created to help public agencies and other organizations manage and share water-related data.

13. Pattern: Meaning-making takes resources

- a. **Description:** In order for data to be broadly useful, it must be analyzed, transformed, visualized, or otherwise processed. Community groups with limited time or statistical capacity can often get stuck with useful data but an inability to interpret it for their purposes. Large, government datasets are often overwhelming, poorly curated, or difficult to access or use for localized environmental action. Figuring out how to make data useful and relevant for specific initiatives requires tailored support because thresholds for action can be highly contextual. This takes time and resources.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers, Researchers, Community Organizations
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Co-develop goals:** Assess communities' data interpretation needs, and co-develop analysis plans.

- See Resources i, ii
- ii. **Match analysis with capacity:** Provide or connect communities with analysts (e.g., academic partners, data fellows, public interest technologists) who can help translate raw data into actionable formats.
 - See Resources i, ii, iii, iv
- iii. **Build shared workflows:** Develop repeatable, understandable workflows for analyzing and communicating data that community members can eventually lead or sustain.
 - See Resources i, ii
- iv. **Use layered storytelling:** Combine data with qualitative information (like lived experience or oral histories) to create outputs that are locally meaningful.
 - See Resources i, ii
- v. **Actionalize your data:** Work with your local university's environmental law clinic to better understand your data's role in regulation and enforcement.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org

Resources

- i. [The 2016 National Advisory Council for Environmental Policy and Technology \(NACEPT\) report](#) includes a framework showing the spectrum of data uses in participatory science.
- ii. [Action's Participatory Science Toolkit Against Pollution](#) addresses the practical problems that participatory scientists face throughout the different stages of each project. It draws on expertise in participatory science, participatory design, social innovation, socio-economic studies, pollution, open science, social computing, open data and software development to ensure it suits the requirements of participatory science projects.
- iii. [DataKind](#) brings together pro bono data scientists and social sector experts to use data science and AI for social impact.
- iv. [Code for America](#) partners with governments and communities to build digital tools and services that make public systems more effective and equitable.

Theme: Academic culture and norms

Responsive and accessible open infrastructure requires a level of dynamism that can be incompatible with academia's slower-moving culture and career advancement pathways that prioritize journal publications. Projects that seek to develop open infrastructure, whether for broad use or for specific contexts, should discuss, negotiate, and align norms around timelines and collaboration rhythms.

14. Pattern: Frontline communities' and academia's differing norms, time frames, and practices

- a. **Description:** Environmental researchers are part of epistemic communities whose norms and time frames are often incompatible with the needs and cultures of more place- and trust-based frontline communities. Communities may value practical, immediate responses to urgent problems over abstract or long-term investigations into root causes. Conversely, community partners may have been tackling an environmental problem for generations (and will continue doing so after research partnerships have ended), while academics must target publication in journals or funding opportunities that prioritize novelty. Furthermore, academic norms around publication, scientific rigor, and problem-framing may not align with what communities see as urgent or valuable. These differing norms and timeframes can create tension between the urgency of community actions, academic incentives and constraints, and the time-intensive production of open knowledge.
- b. **Audience:** Community organizations, Researchers, Research institutions, Funders
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Plan for an “open-first” approach:** Prioritize transparency and accessibility, as well as disciplinary rigor. Acknowledge, resource, and plan for the necessity of an open-first approach. Apply methods and communication that are understandable and usable outside academia, even if that means *temporarily* setting aside formal academic outputs. Prepare templates for quick technical reports that can be shared quickly with communities.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
 - ii. **Train academic scientists in community-collaborative methods:** Provide capacity-building for academic partners in participatory research, power-sharing, and culturally grounded engagement practices.
 - See Resources i

- iii. **Use participatory diagnostics:** Jointly assess the limits and opportunities of the research with community members. Clarify which questions can be answered now and which ones may require longer-term work.
 - See Resources ii
- iv. **Translate findings for action:** Share results in accessible, digestible, and jargon-free formats. Clearly label what is conclusive, what is preliminary, and what is speculative.
 - See Resources i, iii
- v. **Align research outputs with community priorities:** Let community-defined concerns guide how to frame questions and what constitutes a valuable outcome. Be transparent about what academic constraints may prevent or delay.
 - See Resources iv
- vi. **Transform incentives within research institutions:** University expectations of their faculty and research staff may limit the ability for academic partners to commit to long-term collaborations or implement deeper collaboration practices by prioritizing academic publications and conferences over more accessible outputs and communications. Requirements for tenure and promotion could be revised to value collaborative, open research. Institutions and funders could also offer seed funding and other support to enable researchers, especially those early in their career, to invest in community-based partnerships.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
- vii. **Build intergenerational solidarity in pushing for norm change and institutional reform:** Research institutions often see community engagement as secondary to publication in researchers' career advancement pathways. Senior academics are especially well positioned to support and advocate for the recognition of community engagement, open infrastructure work, and continuity in collaborations as meaningful indicators in degree conferral, hiring, promotion, and tenure processes. They can also help normalize community-centered practices by implementing them in research projects, including in collaborations with junior colleagues.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org

Resources

- i. [Community-owned and Managed Research](#) (COMR) is a community-centered research model developed by the West End Revitalization Association to encourage methods that lead to “corrective action of environmental justice (EJ) problems in affected communities.”
- ii. [“What is the Delphi Method and How Do You Use it In Surveys?”](#) outlines a participatory diagnostic method for surveys. This method involves conducting a series of surveys in order to reach a general consensus.
- iii. [The Data Ethics Toolkit](#) from the Association for Advancing Participatory Sciences includes a worksheet on Report Backs that can enable community members to apply research findings or data effectively.
- iv. [Community-Based Environmental Protection: A Resource Book for protecting Ecosystems and Communities](#) offers practical approaches and tools for communities to protect local ecosystems

and enhance environmental health. It includes case studies, strategies, and guidance on organizing, goal-setting, and evaluating community-based environmental protection efforts.

15. Pattern: Readiness for collaboration

- a. **Description:** Academic researchers and engineers may engage in research without having the level of social-cultural understanding or experience needed to develop appropriate strategies. They often lack training in participatory methods, facilitation, or cultural humility—skills critical to effective community partnerships. Without this expertise, collaborations can replicate extractive dynamics that marginalize community voices. Additionally, researchers sometimes assume the role of gatekeepers to communities, positioning themselves as intermediaries without being asked to do so.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers, Researchers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Build capacity through targeted training:** Provide academic researchers and engineers with training in community-collaborative research methods, including cultural humility, participatory facilitation, power-sharing approaches, and popular education techniques.
 - See Resources i, iii
 - ii. **Center community leadership in project design:** Work with civil society organizations and community representatives to delegate appropriate responsibilities (e.g., defining key terms, shaping research questions, or advising on data collection) to community partners. Ensure fair compensation for their time and expertise.
 - See Resources i, ii, iii
 - iii. **Adopt participatory educational approaches:** Use popular education methods to support mutual learning and co-creation of knowledge, helping to balance expertise and create a more inclusive research environment.
 - See Resources i, iii, iv

Resources

- i. [Cultural Humility Resources](#) from UC Berkeley compiles resources to help educators and practitioners develop cultural humility, emphasizing self-reflection, lifelong learning, and respectful engagement with diverse communities. It features articles, toolkits, and videos to support inclusive teaching and practice.
- ii. The Civic Laboratory for Environmental Action Research (CLEAR) has prepared [guidance on how to run equitable lab meetings](#). While this guide was written with academic labs in mind, the resources it points to, such as those related to consensus-based decision making, can be adapted for community collaborations centered on equity, humility, and good relations.
- iii. [Cultural Competency in Research](#) provides an overview of cultural competence in health and social science research, including key concepts, best practices, and recommended resources. It is designed to help researchers incorporate cultural awareness and sensitivity into their work.
- iv. The [Community Tool Box](#) by the University of Kansas outlines essential facilitation skills for leading effective group discussions and meetings. It offers practical tips, techniques, and examples to foster participation, resolve conflicts, and achieve group goals.

Theme: Situational collaboration practices

The success and longevity of open infrastructure often depend on effective collaborations. These in turn rely on governance mechanisms that match the needs of the project, clear expectations about roles, responsibilities, and practices in collaborative relationships, frequent communication, and planning for the future.

16. Pattern: Overly complex governance

- a. **Description:** Open communities often aspire to strong governance structures—specifically those supporting openness as a value. However, when these governance models become overly complex or formalized, they can unintentionally create barriers to participation and reinforce existing power dynamics within the open ecosystem.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Adopt flexible, minimal governance structures** that grow with projects and coalitions as needs emerge. Emphasize transparent decision-making and, where possible, embed those decisions into existing community organizing practices, rather than imposing formal tech governance models.
 - See Resources i, ii
 - ii. **Keep a ‘Future To Do’ list:** Acknowledge the things that still need to be done that can be better accomplished when capacity increases or higher priority items have been completed.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
 - iii. **Include non-technical collaborators in governance decisions:** Complex terminology can create barriers that prevent valuable input from partners with different experiences or levels of expertise. Where possible, use plain language in governance documentation.
 - See Resources iii

Resources

- i. [Building Welcoming Communities](#) explores the importance of governance in open source communities, offering advice on creating clear structures, decision-making processes, and codes of conduct. It helps project leaders build inclusive, sustainable, and well-governed communities.
- ii. [CommunityRule](#) is a toolkit for structuring collaborative governance and role-sharing useful for "open maintainers."
- iii. OKFN's "[Open data governance and open governance: interplay or disconnect?](#)" examines the relationship between open data governance and open governance, discussing whether they complement or conflict with each other. It highlights real-world examples and offers insights on aligning data practices with transparent decision-making.

17. Pattern: Partners and clients have different needs

- a. **Description:** Different types of community collaborators have different expectations. Developers commonly default to a client-service mindset, delivering solutions based on requirements, timelines, and payments. However, open infrastructure efforts thrive when communities are treated not just as end-users, but rather as active partners in co-design. These partnerships emphasize shared ownership, iterative development, and long-term sustainability over polished deliverables.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers, Community Organizations
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Identify the nature of each relationship early:** Are you providing a service or building something together?
 - See Resources i
 - ii. **Develop working agreements that reflect the relationship type:** Include expectations around communication, flexibility, and ownership.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
 - iii. **Develop and employ different models of support depending on whom you are working with:** Use relational strategies that are specific to the people you are working with. For example, a client may set deadlines, payment schedules, and minimum requirements, but community partners may require more flexible timelines and iterative goals or outputs.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
 - iv. **Encourage alignment where possible:** Identify moments where improvements can be made to further community goals. For example, align client projects with open standards to benefit future community reuse.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org

Resources

- i. Nature Canada's '[A Guide To Engagement Organizing](#)' is a good approach to organizing communities of participants. The guide outlines recruitment, designing diverse engagement pathways, surfacing leaders, and tracking.

18. Pattern: Iterative tool development can create instability

- a. **Description:** While iteration is key to improving functionality and a fundamental part of agile development, constant iteration can create instability for users who rely on certain features and stable tools. Even when community input is sought, demanding extra time and overburdening community members with tasks creates instability and deteriorates trust.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Design for stability:** Build tools with intuitive interfaces that don't require extensive training, and consider a range of user expertise levels. Keep things simple to start, and iterate as needed.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
 - ii. **Communicate clearly and openly:** Communicate release schedules as necessary, and plan for mentoring programs for power users, or training or demonstrations for the general public.
 - See Resources i, ii
 - iii. **Support varying user needs:** Offer Long-Term Support versions for stability alongside more experimental or fast-moving releases.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org

Resources

- i. The Engine Room offers practical guides on documentation catered to working with civil society organizations including [documenting when there's so much other work to do](#) and [creating documentation for non-technical audiences](#).
- ii. [Keep a change log](#) or a curated, chronologically ordered list of notable changes for each version of a project.

19. Pattern: Plan for the future

- a. **Description:** Frontline community concerns, priorities, and strategies shift over time. While this can complicate technical and research timelines, the ability to pivot and be responsive to emerging scenarios is important when working on environmental issues. Researchers' ability to commit to long-term engagements may shift: students and early-career researchers often move between institutions or positions as their careers progress or pivot; funding may or may not accompany or accommodate these transitions, which can create challenges for project continuity.
- b. **Audience:** Community Organizations, Researchers, OS Developers, Funders, Research Institutions
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Plan for the long term:** Regularly revisit and revise long-term goals with all stakeholders.

- See Resources i, ii
- ii. **Build in cycles of reflection:** Allocate dedicated time in project timelines for shared reflection and recalibration. This helps teams continuously adjust their work to remain aligned with community goals and evolving environmental conditions.
 - See Resources iii
- iii. **Document for Continuity:** Prioritize open, accessible documentation and interoperable tools. This ensures that new contributors can build on past work without needing to start from scratch.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
- iv. **Advocate for collaborative data and publication policies:** Where possible, researchers can advocate for data and publication policies that support responsible and reciprocal collaboration with communities. Seek advice from your institution’s legal offices or libraries to understand what policies apply, where there’s room for change, or where duly justified exceptions can be made. Identify and consult with allies, and prepare arguments to make with your institution’s relevant offices. Depending on the extent of the collaboration, consider co-authorship on research outputs.
 - See Resources v, vi, vii
- v. **Consider new structures of collaboration:** Look for partners that complement your team’s work and consider building power and combining resources through a merger.
 - See Resources iv
- vi. **Establish shared leadership:** Structure projects with multiple co-leaders (e.g., Co-PIs) from both academic institutions and community organizations. This leadership model should be equitable, ensuring that decision-making power, resources, and credit are shared rather than concentrated into one academic institution.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org

Resources

- i. [Three Horizons Foresight Method](#) explains the Three Horizons framework, a foresight tool for exploring and managing transitions toward sustainable futures. It guides users through identifying current challenges, envisioning long-term goals, and mapping pathways for change.
- ii. [Scenario Planning](#) offers guidance on using scenario-based approaches to build climate resilience and inform adaptation strategies. It includes step-by-step instructions, case studies, and tools for engaging stakeholders in envisioning future climate scenarios.
- iii. [Co-design as a service: Methodological guide](#) includes an introduction to the world of co-design, where the main definitions and mindsets of co-design and design thinking are given, as well as some tools to start applying the creative methodologies within them.
- iv. The [Stanford Social Innovation Review](#) outlines how mergers and acquisitions can be a powerful strategy for nonprofit organizations to grow their impact.
- v. Consider working with [Technology Transfer Offices within universities](#) on strategies to develop training materials and activities, foster connections, and identify community champions at universities.

- vi. [CURIOSS](#) is a community for people who run Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs) at universities and research institutions. They create spaces for collaboration, developing shared tools and information, in addition to promoting the importance of open source software in the academic world.
- vii. The [Civic Laboratory for Environmental Action](#) outlines a process for deciding the order of authors on publications in a way that is fair and responsible. They provide guidance for recognizing all types of contributions beyond writing such as data collection, facilitation, and even emotional labor.

Theme: Long-term sustainability

The long-term viability of open infrastructure depends on securing resources for ongoing maintenance, finding a balance between scale and specificity, and supporting local champions.

20. Pattern: Open tools need ongoing maintenance

- a. **Description:** Open source tools often end up in the “graveyard”: unmaintained, under-documented, and ultimately unknown. Lack of a plan for lifecycle or handoff can make it harder to build on what came before.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Explore financially sustainable models:** Consider commercialization, cooperative ownership, or hybrid open-proprietary models to fund long-term maintenance.
 - See Resources i
 - ii. **Embed sustainability early:** To create a more adaptable and long-lasting technology infrastructure, design for interoperability from the start. Enabling platforms to connect and share information with less friction can ensure that they remain useful for longer.
 - See Resources ii, iii, iv
 - iii. **Plan for transitions:** Define ownership, handoff, or archiving strategies early on. Identify long-term stewards or institutions who can take over maintenance if needed.
 - See Resources iv
 - iv. **Develop a plan for sharing and supporting existing tools:** Consider building interoperability into existing projects or tools, rather than creating redundant ones.
 - See Resources i, ii, iii, iv
 - v. **Make the case for funding:** Document use cases, community impact, and maintenance needs to secure funding for tool longevity.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org

Resources

- i. Special organizations exist for the purpose of fiscally sponsoring projects. While each project has individual needs that should be independently assessed, a non-conclusive list of Fiscal Sponsorship providers includes: [Open Source Collective](#), [Aspiration Technology](#), [Allied Media Foundation](#), [Code for Science and Society](#), and [Open Science Hardware Foundation](#).
- ii. [CHAOSS Project](#) (Community Health Analytics for Open Source Software) provides metrics for evaluating the health and sustainability of open source communities.
- iii. [The Open Source Way](#) is a guidebook on how to build sustainable open source communities.
- iv. The [Software Sustainability Institute](#) offers guidance and tools for software lifecycle planning and handoff strategies.

21. Pattern: Balancing Scale and Specificity

- a. **Description:** Developers who aim for generalizability and scalability in their tools often sacrifice place-based specificity and alignment. On the other hand, development projects that prioritize local needs first and treat generalizability as a secondary goal may sacrifice broad applicability and financial sustainability.
- b. **Audience:** OS Developers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Embrace modularity and layered design:** Use modular architectures, layered ontologies, and flexible interfaces to allow both broad applicability and local adaptation.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
 - ii. **Center real-world use cases:** Develop and document localized case studies to illustrate practical implementations and inform further tool design based on real community needs.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
 - iii. **Design with and for communities:** Design with communities while prioritizing interoperability and integrating familiar features so that tools can interact easily with other digital infrastructure. Interoperability, open source development, and thorough documentation can also facilitate iteration in tool design, allowing future developers to adapt tools for evolving community needs or broader purposes.
 - See Resources i
 - iv. **Support participation:** Build community capacity to interact with the open source development process so that they can suggest feasible features.
 - See Resources ii, iii
 - v. **Cultivate ecosystems of care:** For widely used tools, cultivate a cross-sector community of practice so that users have an accessible venue for providing input. For tools specific to a geography or project, support networks of “open maintainers” to foster cross-community collaboration; maintainers can share responsibilities across projects while users can offer input around clusters of related tools.
 - See Resources iii

Resources

- i. "[Design Justice](#)" by Sasha Costanza-Chock offers strategies for ensuring tools are responsive to community-defined needs and identities, without universalizing or flattening them.
- ii. GitHub's "[New to open source? Here's everything you need to get started](#)" is a guide to the world of open source. It includes how to find projects, understand contribution guidelines and the tools for participating in open source.
- iii. The [Public Lab Code Community](#) provided a model for reciprocity-based systems. "First-timer-only issues" allowed newcomers to learn coding while also contributing to the maintenance of the tool. Mentors then migrated upward in the community. Developers can look to this approach to build community capacity to interact with and make direct improvements to software.

22. Pattern: Champions within civil society organisations need more support

- a. **Description:** Many participatory science initiatives rely heavily on local champions and community members to bridge the gap between scientists and the public. Yet these individuals, typically based at civil society organisations or in grassroots groups, often receive the least training, mentorship, and recognition.
- b. **Audience:** Community Organizations, Researchers
- c. **Solutions:**
 - i. **Create structured support mechanisms:** Develop dedicated funding streams, targeted training programs, and accessible resources that directly empower local champions.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
 - ii. **Develop mentorship and peer networks:** Facilitate cross-community learning by establishing mentorship programs and regional or thematic peer support networks.
 - Resources needed, please suggest one at digitcore.openenvironmentaldata.org
 - iii. **Include and recognize champions:** Ensure early and explicit involvement of local champions in project planning and design. Formal recognition, such as authorship or stipends, should also be used.
 - See Resources i

Resources

- i. The [Civic Laboratory for Environmental Action](#) outlines a process for deciding the order of authors on publications in a way that is fair and responsible. They provide guidance for recognizing all types of contributions beyond writing such as data collection, facilitation, and even emotional labor.

III. Acknowledgments

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IV. Glossary

Successful environmental research and development collaborations start with clear and mutual understandings of terminology. This glossary defines the main concepts from the Toolkit that are the most useful to develop this mutual understanding and facilitate implementation of the patterns.

Biopiracy: The practices and activities that lead to the appropriation and privatization of biological resources stewarded by indigenous peoples or local communities, as well as knowledge related to these resources. Biopiracy is associated with individuals or institutions asserting intellectual property rights without appropriately informing or obtaining consent from the communities who steward biological resources.

Co-design: Iterative and collaborative processes that include diverse stakeholders in jointly coming up with project ideas or solutions, bringing together a wide range of expertise, perspectives and backgrounds to create more context-specific and relevant outcomes, and employing participatory techniques.

Co-development: The collaborative definition and implementation of a project or initiative, in which there are opportunities for equitable participation and engagement throughout multiple research phases and involving all relevant parties from the outset.

Commons: The combination of a resource, a community that gathers around that resource, and a set of rules to care for the resource and its resultant community. The “commons” can be associated with both natural resources as well as “peer-to-peer” knowledge sharing networks built on digital or internet infrastructure.

Community organizations: When we use the term “community organizations,” we are generally referring to what the United Nations calls [Civil Society Organizations](#), or “any non-profit, voluntary citizens’ group which is organized on a local, national or international level. Task-oriented and driven by people with a common interest, civil society organisations (CSOs) perform a variety of services and humanitarian functions, bring citizens’ concerns to Governments, monitor policies, and encourage political participation at the community level.” In the context of this toolkit, they tend to be organized around geographically-situated environmental issues or interests. They may be formal not-for-profit organizations or less formal groups of neighbors with shared goals. They may also serve as intermediaries between individual members of frontline communities on the one hand and industry, government, research, or technology firms on the other.

Community Review Boards (CRBs): Groups of community members who have a stake in research to be conducted and can represent the interests and perspectives of their fellow community members. As an alternative or supplement to Institutional Review Boards, CRBs provide

community oversight and accountability to communities who stand to be impacted by research rather than only research participants or “human subjects.” They may provide feedback on research design and communications materials, and may even review data before it is shared publicly to check assumptions. A somewhat recent practice (as of 2025), CRBs have been increasingly consulted in health research.

Cooperative data ownership: The rights and practices associated with controlling and processing data by multiple collaborating entities, including the ability to store, access, modify, analyze, and share data. Cooperative models involve multiple stakeholders in these tasks, allowing for various data producers or collectors to contribute to definitions and stewardship. For more on cooperative data ownership, see OEDP’s [Data Decoder](#) on the topic.

Data governance: The framework and practices that defines the who, what, where, how, when, and why of managing and utilizing data by an individual, organization, or other collective. These encompass the policies, roles, processes, and standards necessary to ensure that data is accurate, consistent, secure, and used responsibly. For more on data governance, see OEDP’s [Data Decoder](#) on the topic.

Indigenous data sovereignty: A principle meant to assure that indigenous communities are entitled to lead or participate in the governance of data produced, shared, or collected by or about them. Useful frameworks to support indigenous data sovereignty include the [CARE Principles](#) (which refer to collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility, and ethics), and The First Nations Principles of [OCAP](#) (or ownership, control, access, and possession). Indigenous data sovereignty practices aim to avoid the exploitation of indigenous communities for their data without any reciprocal benefits.

Data use agreement or **Data sharing agreement:** Agreed upon and collaboratively defined practices or processes regarding the use and eventual sharing of data produced or collected in a project, setting the expectations, exceptions, and mechanisms for review and accountability.

Epistemic communities: Groups that share specific sets of practices and mechanisms for producing and validating knowledge (usually in the context of professional or scientific fields). These practices and mechanisms are embedded in epistemic communities’ empirical approaches, tools, and methodologies. Without responsible or inclusive collaboration practices, these may create fragmentation and obstacles for knowledge sharing.

FAIR: An acronym for the principles and accompanying guidelines to promote the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and re-usability of data, metadata, and other digital assets, emphasizing the benefit of computational systems interacting with data with no or minimal human intervention. For more on FAIR, see [The GO FAIR Initiative](#).

Free and Open Source: Free and Open Source, or [open source](#) more generally, refers to hardware, software, tools, and projects that are freely available for anyone to use, modify, and distribute. Free and Open Source communities go beyond technical specifications and attempt to develop a way of working that is rooted in collaboration, innovation, and transparency, sharing knowledge and iterating through problem solving.

Frontline communities: Geographically identifiable collectives bearing a disproportionate burden of environmental pollution and/or hazards posed by climate change. In the context of this toolkit, these groups use or attempt to use open infrastructures in their efforts to understand environmental processes or to address environmental justice problems like pollution.

Funders: Funders are public agencies, private foundations, companies and other sources of capital that provide funding for research and technology development in the form of grants, awards, or venture capital. Like research institutions, they may also govern research and development practices by imposing requirements on those they fund (e.g., open licensing or reporting practices).

Metadata: Data providing information about data, including descriptive elements that enable others to find, trace, and potentially reuse data resources. Metadata can be provided in a range of formats, from free text to structured and machine-readable, following standards recommended by scientific fields, disciplines, or other data-oriented communities for optimal utility.

Obscuring identifying information: In the context of data sharing, techniques or practices implemented to avoid sharing sensitive information publicly or with unauthorized individuals, while still allowing for data usability for established purposes. This may include de-identifying data by removing personally identifiable information, such as names or contact information, from published datasets, for example.

Open infrastructure (OI): Technological tools and services that support and enable open research practices. OI groups the elements that facilitate the dissemination, preservation, and accessibility of research outputs such as publications, data, software, and hardware. OI fosters collaboration as well as the adoption of open standards, ensuring the transparency, reusability, reproducibility, and long-term sustainability of environmental research.

Open source technologists: People, initiatives, and companies developing digital and data infrastructure, monitoring devices or tools using open source practices, and often for the purposes of making designs, code, data, or other resources available and accessible to the public to use, replicate, or learn from, regardless of their affiliation to the original project. In the context of this project, they may be working in collaboration with researchers or frontline communities to develop technology to make sense of environmental and socio-environmental phenomena.

Participatory diagnosis: Strategies to support collective or participatory decision-making in research and interventions, with the goal of better contextualizing research questions, designs, and methods. These may entail reciprocal processes of knowledge sharing and production, where it can be helpful for researchers to be open to changing their assumptions and research norms. Helpful instruments might include semi-structured interviews, cross-sectional paths, participatory mapping, and community workshops.

Participatory science: Approaches and traditions that emphasize public or community contributions to research. This is sometimes referred to as “citizen science,” “community science,” or “volunteer monitoring,” among other terms, though these may have varying definitions depending on the context. Some initiatives are scientist-driven, with researchers inviting volunteers to get involved in different tasks, while others are community-driven, or co-created between researchers, communities, and others, leveraging science to gather evidence and address problems of interest.

Patterns: Recurring arrangements or characteristics that we found across contexts, and that provide a foundation for repeatable ways to solve common issues. In the context of open infrastructure development, these are the challenges, problems, and phenomena experienced or observed by the people we spoke with. In identifying patterns, we hope to offer a shared language and understanding, enabling multiple actors to discuss ideas and perspectives and collaborate more effectively.

Research institutions: Research institutions are formal organizations that staff researchers and govern their practices at a high level (e.g., imposing ethical review processes, openness practices, or intellectual property requirements). They include: universities, national laboratories, public research agencies, think tanks, and nonprofit research organizations. While they may staff environmental researchers or focus on environmental research, their interests often extend beyond environmental questions.

Researchers: Researchers are people and groups collecting information to answer environmental questions in collaboration with frontline communities. They may be affiliated with formal institutions, work more independently, or be members of frontline communities themselves. They may also be developing or using open technology. Researchers are one of the key audiences for this toolkit.

Relational openness: The practices of participation and transparency in collaborative decision-making processes, as well as communication and sharing of resources with collaborative approaches.

Schema: A blueprint for the structure and organization of data within a database, including relationships between where data are stored and shared, as well as constraints imposed on what data can enter a system, and how data is accessed or shared.

Ontologies: Descriptions and definitions of the types of relationships that can exist among a set of data elements. These go beyond mere structure and are more specific to a domain or subject area.

User personas: Fictional characteristics attributed to potential audiences that may use a product or service under development. Personas are created through research processes that include techniques such as interviews, surveys, data analytics, with the purpose of making products more tailored to the needs, behaviors, and goals of probable users. They can be combined with other user-centered design techniques, such as empathy maps or participatory diagnosis, in order to increase products' usability and improve communities' experiences of tools and technologies.

DIGITCORE

OPEN ENVIRONMENTAL DATA PROJECT